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MESSAGES FOR MANKIND: GUIDELINES FOR COMMON WELFARE

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Abstract

This research has been developed with general scope but with an special topic for educational purposes, highlighting the benefits of promoting educational work concerning to the importance of taking into account the education for peace and the common good, perhaps as one of the main tasks of education. In this context, it is usually not clear how we should teach about the peace in the lessons, it is challenging to explore the manner to teach this topic, so this document provides an example and practical knowledge about this concern. So, a premise in this document is the fact that peace and common good should be one of the fundamental purposes of any educated society

The Vatican, Holy See, in our current History plays an important roll in geopolitical matters that generates changes that are happening worldwide, always looking for the common good. The Pope Francis is one of the most recognized leaders that represent a remarkable influence during this second decade of the 21st century, and it is to be expected that his leadership will lead to changes for the international community in order to promote peace, stability and harmony.

Considering the geopolitical perspective, the Vatican and the Pope Francisco represent an important influence to deliver and share relevant messages and suggestions for mankind, suggestions that as leaders as Governments in addition to other important international organizations, they are always open to listen and to understand.

It is interesting to analyze the impact that Holy See has in order to influence in a positive manner in geopolitics, for the benefit of the common good. First of all, it is undeniable the global political leadership by the Pope Francis; Second, it is relevant to consider the influence of Christianity as an important ideological support of the Western world and that it even have an important friendly dialogue with other faiths and religions; and third, it is important to take in to account the influence and diplomacy of the Holy See, which has proven great contributions in benefit of resolving international conflicts.

This research analyze interesting messages and press releases through which the Holy See and specially with the inspiration of Pope Francis, has made important contributions for the good of mankind in the promotion of the common welfare for all, bringing a series of teachings and useful guidelines to consider in the ongoing global crisis that faces the international community in this century.

Keywords:

Holy See, Pope Francis, press releases

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1 CHRISTIANITY IN THE HISTORY

Christianity is the religion founded by Jesus Christ and those who profess this religion are incorporated by baptism, thus belonging to the community that is taken into account for *the salvation*, this community commonly called Church. The resurrection of Jesus Christ is the central dogma of Christianity and this is the most important fact on which is based all the truth of this doctrine. Jesus Christ not only founded the religion of Christianity, he also founded the Church that must be led by Peter, whom Christ promised the primacy of the Church and also Jesus said that this Church should remain until the end of time [1].

Since the beginning, the most important leaders of Christianity were the Apostles; they were obedient to the command of Christ. Due to the lack of historical sources, it is not easy to identify the way in which the Apostle Peter arrived in Rome to become the first bishop of the capital of the Roman Empire. It is possible that Peter began his path from Palestine, passing through Antioch, in order to subsequently arrive at Rome to promote and expand the Christianity under the political and cultural context of the Roman Empire. Since the early stages of Christianity the Bishop of Rome, which has been represented in successive manner by the Apostle Peter, exercised the primacy over the Church and the Eucharist Rite since the beginning has always represented the Central Point of Christian life [2].

Around the fourth century, the transit of tolerance to religious freedom occurred quickly with the Emperor Constantine. This happened until the Roman Empire was separated into two parts, East and West, division consummated at the end of the fourth century, event that had a major impact on the life of the Church. In this context, the western part of the Roman Empire coincided with the regions of Latin culture and language; in other hand, the Eastern largely encompassed cultures Greek, Syrian, and Coptic, being the cities of Alexandria, Antioch and Jerusalem the main ecclesiastical circumscriptions of East part of Roman Empire and Christianity [3].

Later, after the Council of Chalcedon, in the year 451, the Bishop of Rome was established giving him the “primacy of honor” over all the Christian Church, with the absolute recognition of his authority in the doctrinal field, but disregarding any authority discipline and jurisdiction of the Popes on the Eastern Churches. The years after the fifth century, are considered to the centuries that followed to the conversion of the old world, and in that period was developed with greater precision the Christian doctrine with the following fundamental truths: the dogmatic doctrines of the Holy Trinity, the Mystery of Christ, and the doctrine of Grace [4]

Finally, it should be noted in the historical process of Christianity a fundamental fact, that represents one of the most important contributions to mankind. During the medieval period is considered to Christianity as a religion that was and strategic protagonist who promoted the development of a transcendent institution until our days, and earnestly promotes the development of sacred sciences by an institution destined to create and to develop science and to spread the culture: the University. In this sense, it is considered the University of Paris as the first entity to complete this process of higher education institution, and by the year 1215, Pope Innocent III confirmed the privileges that guaranteed in those moments the autonomy of this French Institution. Later, throughout the 13th century the Universities of Oxford, Bologna and Salamanca, were those that highlighted the Universalist spirit of Christianity [5].

2 THE VATICAN AND ITS GLOBAL PLAYER ROLL

The Vatican is considered as a special case mainly because it is a State that, at the same time, is the Headquarter or main Office of a religion. The Vatican was established as a State since February 11, 1929, according to the Lateran Pacts of 1929 or Lateran Accords, establishing the independence from Italy. So, the Vatican is situated in Mediterranean Europe in particular inside of the city of Rome, covering an area of approximately 3 square kilometers. The current population of the Vatican is of approximately 1,000 inhabitants, where the main religion is Catholic. As a State and system of Government, the Vatican is a monarchical Priestly State of the Catholic Church, with a Unicameral Pontifical Commission. This State has formally made its Constitution in 1967, called "Apostolic Constitution". The Vatican is not an active Member State for the United Nations system, but it is an observer state for the United Nations. The Vatican is a landlocked territory located in Rome, Italy, and formally representing the smallest State in the world. Apart from the territorial limits of Vatican City, thanks to the Lateran treaties of 1929 it has been awarded extra-territorial authority of the Holy See over 23 sites in Rome and five outside of Rome, including the Pontifical Palace of Castelgandolfo, the summer residence of the Pope [6].

In the next Figure, it is shown the flag and the map of its location in Europe (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Flag and location in Europe: The Vatican

Source: Central Intelligence Agency. [7]

The flag of the Vatican represents the next ideas. First, there are two vertical bands of yellow and white, depicting the arms of the Holy See. Second, it is shown the crossed keys of St. Peter, crowned by the papal tiara of three levels. And third, the yellow color in the flag represents the spiritual power of the Pope, while the white color represents its power in the world as a human or part of the mankind.

Popes in their secular role have historically ruled portions of the Italian peninsula for more than thousand years until the mid-19th century, when many of the Papal States were seized by the Kingdom of Italy. In 1870 the possessions of the Popes were also limited when Rome was finally annexed to the Kingdom of Italy. Subsequently, disputes between the Italian Government due to the concern relate with a series of Popes prisoners in Italy were resolved in 1929 by the Lateran Treaties,

which established the independent State of the Vatican City and with this fact, it had been settled Catholicism with an special status in Italy [8].

Subsequently, disputes between the Italian Government and the Catholicism were due to the concern related with a series of Popes prisoners in Italy, and these disputes were resolved in 1929 thanks to the Lateran Treaties, which established the independent State of the Vatican City and with this fact, it had been settled Catholicism with an special status in Italy. Decades later, in 1984, an agreement between the Holy See and the Government of Italy amended some of the accords of the Lateran treaties, including the primacy of Catholicism as the official Italian religion [9].

Currently, diverse concerns occupy the Holy See and these themes include religious freedom, development policy and international economics, the deterioration of the environment, the constant instability in the region of the Middle East, the evolution of global geo-politics, the decline of religion in Europe, terrorism, interreligious dialogue and reconciliation, and application of the doctrine of the Catholic Church in an age of rapid change and in a context of Globalization. According statistics, it is estimated that at least 1.2 billion people worldwide profess the Catholic faith. In the United Nations system, the Vatican is only an observer State, similar as in the cases of Palestine and Taiwan [10].

Finally, the Treaty of Lateran in 1929 (signed at the time by Pietro Gasparri as the Secretary of State of the Holy See and on behalf of Pope Pius XI, and by the Prime Minister of Italy Benito Mussolini), highlighted the following honors by Italy with regard to the Vatican State [11]:

- a. Italy recognizes and reaffirms the principle that the Catholic Religion, Apostolic and Roman, is recognized as the only religion of the State.
- b. Italy recognizes the sovereignty of the Holy see for international purposes, as attribute inherent to their nature in accordance with its tradition and the demands of its mission in the world.
- c. Italy recognizes the Holy See full ownership, and and its absolute authority and sovereign jurisdiction over the Vatican, with their belongings and endowments, creating for this objective the Vatican City for special purposes and with the modalities that dictate the Lateran treaties.
- d. Sovereignty and exclusive jurisdiction that Italy recognizes the Holy See over the Vatican City, must not suffer any interference by the Italian Government and Italy recognizes that there is no other authority than the Holy See in The Vatican City.

3 POPE FRANCIS

On March 13, 2013, with the words "Habemus Papam", Jorge Mario Bergoglio, Archbishop of Buenos Aires, takes its name from Francisco in reference to the poor of Assisi, in order to promote a "Church poor and for the poor". This has been considered as an ideal Pope for the reform of the Catholic Church, even he has been considered as "a new John XXIII" [11].

Pope Francis is considered as a humble Pope, who improvises and promotes a poor Church. Pope Francis seems to be destined to carry out the major challenges that the world of the 21st century demands to solve, challenges for the Church represented among others by cleaning its own institution due to fails and also scandals, the reform of the Curia, the commitment to collective responsibility, the role of laymen and women, ecumenism, Latin America or China, all these are some of the challenges [13].

Pope Francis is the first American Pope, the continent where lives half of the Catholics of the world, considered as the present and the future of the Catholic Church. At the same time, Francis is the first Jesuit Pope and he has chosen the name of Francisco in honor of the founder of an important religious order, the Jesuits, and with this fact, Francis intends to modify the pole of relevance in the Church by a model promoting a new evangelization marked in the past by the "Opus Dei" or the Legionaries of Christ, and now Pope Francis intends to lead the Church towards the return of the religious life, taking into account that a Jesuit prints character and this charism is represented by the poverty of the Saint of Assisi [14].

Something relevant in this fact is that now with the Pope Francis, for the first time in history, the Pope and his predecessor coexist in the Vatican, with a Pope as the Leader of the Catholic Church and an Emeritus Pope in the person of Benedict XVI.

It is common that Pope Francis has been compared with Pope John XXIII, Pope who was identified fifty years ago as the "good Pope" and he was who convened the Second Vatican Council, considering that at this Council the winter of the Church was replaced for years by the spring, with a new leadership of higher vocational level and freedom. As a result, many specialists compare to Pope Francis with John XXIII, based in the argument that Pope Francis has now the great challenge of reforming the Catholic Church, and in this Century that it is real the latent threat of the impairment or significant loss of influence in the world that used to have by The Vatican. [15].

Pope Francis, Cardinal Jorge Mario Bergoglio, was appointed since March 13, 2013, as the new Pope of the Catholic Church following the recent resignation of Benedict XVI on February 11. As a result of the Conclave on March 13, 2013, the chimney of the Sistine Chapel showed the expected white smoke announcing that the new successor of St.Peter was chosen by the Cardinals saying the formula "Habemus Papam", whereupon Jorge Mario Bergoglio became the new Pope, Bishop of Rome, and which had chosen the name "Francis" for his pontificate. Jorge Mario Bergoglio was the Archbishop of Buenos Aires and was born in Buenos Aires on December 17, 1936. He was ordained priest on December 13, 1969, and years later John Paul II appointed him Bishop in Buenos Aires on June 27, 1992. Subsequently he became Archbishop of Buenos Aires on February 28, 1998, for finally being named Cardinal by the Pope John Paul II on February 21, 2001 [16].

The European Union also has recognized the importance of the leadership that must assume the Pope Francis. The European Union issued a statement desiring for Pope Francis a lengthy and blessed pontificate, with the chance to defend and promote the values of peace, solidarity and human dignity which are values of essential well-being that are needed in a world currently facing many challenges in a context of profound changes. The European Union also expressed the desire to work with his Holiness Francis, in order to continue with determination and strength the work of his predecessors, referring to Pope Benedict XVI and John Paul II, in their efforts to bring together people of different religions and cultures [17].

In addition, the United Nations issued its congratulations by the recently elected Pope Francis. The Secretary-General of the United Nations, Ban Ki-moon, also congratulated all the Catholics and stressed his commitment to continue working in cooperation with the Holy See, because United Nations share the same goals with the Holy See ranging from the promotion of peace, social justice, human rights, and the eradication of poverty and hunger, all of which are essential elements of sustainable development. Therefore, Ban said that United Nations and the Holy See coincide that the challenges of today can be resolved through dialogue, emphasizing the promotion of interreligious dialogue [18].

4 PRESS RELEASES FROM THE HOLLY SEE: IMPORTANT GUIDELINES FOR MANKIND

In this section has been identified a sample of important teachings and guidelines for the benefit of mankind taken from the Holy See, and this ideas have been inspired by the Pope Francis according to the messages that has shared to the international community in the recent past [19].

4.1 The wealth that is not shared generates corruption

On May 25, 2015, the Vatican issued a statement explaining that on this date Pope Francis in his morning homily shared a reflection explaining that the wealth that is not shared generates corruption, stressing in this regard the following. Pope Francis said that it is necessary to encourage those who possess riches and foster them the use of those possessions for service of the common good, avoiding that abundance allow living selfishly, explaining that this situation " is sad, removes hope and generates all kinds of corruption, large or small". In this context, the Pope said that the attachment to the riches is the home of all kinds of corruption: personal corruption, corruption in business, small commercial corruption, political corruption, even mentioning corruption in education.

Pope Francis explained also that all those who live attached to the own power and own wealth, mistakenly believe that they are in paradise, but at the end must leave everything in this world. In this context, the Pope said that "there is a mystery in the possession of riches", arguing that the riches have the ability to seduce and make believe erroneously who possess them that they are in a real paradise on Earth, but what really happens is that this disproportionate attachment to the riches at the end creates sadness, and to avoid this feeling, it is necessary that the wealth must be shared for the common good, for all.

Therefore, in this message Pope Francis appealed to avoid sadness associated with the relentless addiction to wealth, and instead, open the door to the generosity, reason why the Pope shared the following message: *"The first beatitude: Blessed are the poor in spirit, that means, remove this attachment to the goods and make the wealth that the Lord has given us for the common good. The only way is to open hands, open heart. But if you have the closed hand, you have the heart closed as the man who made banquet and is dressed lavishly, a man who don't have horizons, a man who don't see what others need, and so only this man will be far from God"* (Pope Francis).

4.2 Educational service of the Catholic Church

On 3 June, 2015, the Vatican issued a statement explaining that on this date the cardinal Pietro Parolin, the Vatican Secretary of State, participated in an event in commemoration of the 70th anniversary of the founding of UNESCO or United Nations Organization for Education, Science and Culture, emphasizing in this regard the following.

In this commemoration, Cardinal Parolin developed a discourse in which was presented an overview about the history of the educational service of the Catholic Church from its origins, claiming that on the basis of the teaching of the Church it is the biblical anthropology in which appears from Genesis, and taking into account the love relationship and reciprocity between the human being and God.

In addition, Cardinal Parolin appealed to promote around the world a comprehensive and complete education which aims to build the preliminary foundations of an inclusive society, dialogic and peaceful. In this context, Parolin made emphasis on addressing the challenges according to the current

educational perspectives, challenges identified in two clear manners: the challenge of extreme fragmentation of knowledge; and the challenge of the worrying incompatibility between different disciplinary sectors.

Finally, in this discourse Cardinal Parolin reiterated the commitment of the Vatican with the strengthening of education in the world, but clarifying that the Catholic Church did not consider never culture nor education as a mere instruments for evangelization.

In this sense, Cardinal Parolin shared the following message: *"Culture and education have never been considered by the Catholic Church as mere instruments for the evangelization, but as human dimensions of high intrinsic value. Investment in the education of the younger generations is a condition for the development of people, and particularly those who strive to escape from hunger, poverty, endemic diseases, ignorance; seeking a stake more intense in the fruits of civilization, a more active appreciation of human peculiarities, as claimed by Paul VI in the Encyclical Letter Populorum Progressio. Catholic Church agree with the efforts for greater access to literacy, education for all and lifelong learning. These pillars are further strengthened by the fundamental commitment in benefit of ethnic and religious minorities and in support of the female gender, gender that is very important for the harmonious growth of the society"*(Pietro Parolin).

4.3 Food is a right, and a right does not allow exclusions

On June 11, 2015, the Vatican issued a release stating that on this date Pope Francis addressed a speech at the 39th session of the Organization of the United Nations for Food and Agriculture -FAO-, in a session held in the Sala Clementina of the Vatican, standing out the following.

Pope Francis expressed that the international community must keep in mind the situation of many people who suffer from hunger, and for those authorities responsables for managing this situation is important to foster the promotion of agricultural development, considering that this development has become today one of the great challenges in this time of crisis. Also, Pope Francis made a call to the international community to promote and ensure the challenge of access to necessary food, considering to this as a right for all, and in this sense, the Pope stressed that rights do not permit exclusions.

At the same time, Pope Francis also said to the representatives of the FAO, that food security should be achieved taking into account that countries differs by their geographical location, economic conditions or dietary cultures. In this sense, Pope Francis requested to the international community to strengthen the efforts needed to join forces in this challenge and ensure that all persons have access to real food security in terms of a healthy and sufficient food, and in other hand it is necessary to eliminate misconceptions of food security in developed countries that sometimes erroneously identify this situation in terms of to eliminate fat and promote physical activity.

Finally, Pope Francis concluded this intervention by extending the following message encouraging the FAO and the international community to work tirelessly in achieving food security and sustainable development for all the families of the world: *"We must start with our lives if we want to change lifestyles, aware that our small gestures can make sustainability and the future of the human family. We must continue the fight against hunger without ulterior motives. The FAO projections say that for the year 2050, with nine billion people on the planet, the food production has to increase and even double. Rather than be impressed with the data, we must modify our relationship with natural resources, in terms of the use of the soil; modify the consumption without falling into the slavery of consumerism; we must eliminate waste and thus overcome hunger. The Catholic Church with its institutions and initiatives is committed to work with the international community aware that the*

planet's resources are limited and its sustainable use is quite urgent for developing agriculture and food; we must be committed to promote that change of attitude necessary for the good of future generations" (Pope Francis).

4.4 Promote the creation of jobs and opportunities for young people

On June 20, 2015, the Vatican issued a press release expressing that on this date Pope Francisco received in audience in the Sala Clementina of the Apostolic Palace of the Vatican to four hundred members of The National Federation Of the "Cavalieri del Lavoro" (an organization integrated by recognized entrepreneurs in Italy) and Pope Francis extended a message calling them to "invent new ways in the world of work" including the following.

Pope Francis appealed them to promote the creation of employment and opportunities especially for young people, due to job creation which has registered a strong stagnation and a true recession, in a social context already marked by inequalities and unemployment especially of the youth sector after the financial crisis of 2008 and subsequent years. In this context, Pope Francis emphasized to the audience that the unemployment of the youth sector, is considered as a true "social plague" because it deprives an essential element for their realization through getting a job, in a context in which the world economy is incapable of having the valuable contribution of the energies and capacities of young people.

At the same time, Pope Francis added in this regard that the world of work and entrepreneurs should be waiting for young people ready to engage and willing for success, but should provide opportunities to receive to them in their respective industries sectors.

Finally, Pope Francis concluded his intervention by extending the following message to the members of The National Federation Of the "Cavalieri del Lavoro", a group of renowned Italian entrepreneurs, encouraging them to be tireless promoters in the creation of job opportunities for young people: *"The common good, as the ultimate goal of the associated life, cannot be achieved through a mere increase of the profits or production, because it has the active involvement of considering to the workforce as a simple budget. As entrepreneurs, you have been recognized because you have taken risks, have invested in ideas, in energy and providing capital, producing, entrusting tasks, asking for results and helping others to be more entrepreneurial and collaborative. Here we have the social scale of the employment: the ability to engage people and entrusted responsibilities, rising the incitement to boldness, creativity and commitment. The social scope of work life has positive effects on future generations and make a society to begin to look forward, offering prospects and opportunities and, therefore, hope for the future"*(Pope Francis).

4.5 Take care of the planet, is the home of the mankind, our House.

On June 18, 2015, the Vatican issued a statement highlighting the importance of to know the encyclical "Laudato Si", written by Pope Francis, standing out in this respect the following.

In this statement the Vatican points out that the text of this new encyclical letter, which consists of 191 pages distributed in six chapters, takes its name from the invocation of St. Francis of Assisi "Laudato Si, Mi Signore" (praised be you, my Lord), and this document encourage us to remember that Earth is our common home and is also as a sister with whom we share the existence and a beautiful mother who welcomes us in her arms.

In addition, the Vatican said in this release that Pope Francis in this Encyclical is targeting the Catholic faithful bearing in mind the following words of Saint John Paul II: "Christians, in particular, discover that their role in the creation, as well as his duties with the nature and the creator, are part of their faith, especially to enter into dialogue with all of our common home"(Saint John Paul II).

Also, in this statement the Vatican highlights that the concept of "dialogue" appears throughout the text of the Encyclical *Laudato Si*, highlighting that Pope Francis recognizes also that other Churches and Christian communities, as well as other religions, they have developed a deep concern and a valuable reflection on the subject of ecology, recognizing specific contributions of the Ecumenical Patriarch Bartholomew and other protagonists of this effort, both individuals as associations or institutions, scientists, philosophers, theologians and social organizations, which have enriched the thinking of the Church on the importance to recognize the care of Ecology through an integrated approach and, at the same time, contributing in the full development of the human race.

Finally, this press release highlights that in the encyclical "*Laudato Si*", in paragraph 246, Pope Francis shares to the world the following prayer for our land: "Almighty God, that you are present throughout the universe and in the smallest of your creatures, you surround with your tenderness all what exists, pour in us the power of your love that we care for life and beauty. Flood us with peace, so let us live as brothers and sisters without harming anyone. You, God of the poorest, please help us to rescue the abandoned and forgotten of this land, people that have so much worth to your eyes. Please give us a healthy life, and help us to take care of the planet and do not allow the predators to damage the Earth, so permits grow beauty and take away any pollution and destruction. Please touch the hearts of those who seek only profits at the expense of the poor and the Earth. Please teach us to discover the value of everything, to look at, admired, to recognize that we are deeply united with all creatures on our way to your infinite light. Thank you because you are with us every day. Please encourage us, in our struggle for Justice, love and peace." (*Laudato Si*, Pope Francis).

5. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The Vatican represents, beyond the religious aspect and the doctrine of faith, a valuable institution that considers that God, mankind and the planet Earth, represent three key factors that need to be joined in the efforts to achieve a better world for present and future generations. Through their different activities the Vatican promotes messages and guides of action for new forms of cooperation and hope for our civilization, working closely with organizations assigned or not to United Nations System, and also the Vatican promotes dialogue among religions, cultures and races, and different forms of Government. In the current times, under the leadership of Pope Francis the Vatican has a personality open to dialogue and ready to give the best words of encouragement, initiatives, proposals and recommendations of life, not just for Catholics, also for the entire international community.

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